

EFFECT OF SILANE COUPLING AGENTS ON FILLING OF MAGNETIC PARTICLES IN RESIN COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

Noise suppression sheet contains magnetic filler and thermoplastic polymer. As high filling raises the capability, silane treatment has been tried to depress voids in the sheet. Among various kinds of silane, alkyl ammonium silane has given the highest filling. This has been interpreted in terms of silane effect on polymer viscosity.

Keywords: silane treatment / magnetic filler polymeric composites / void / magnetic permeability / polymer viscosity

INTRODUCTION

Recently, there are lots of electronics with high frequency work generating high frequency wave noise where electronic parts is often interfered each other. In order to depress the magnetic noise, noise suppression sheets have been actively developed in Japan [1-3]. The noise suppression sheet is required to have two following efficiencies: First, they have the ability of noise suppression even with thinness of the sheet[4, 5]. Second, the flexibility of the sheet is required to fit the geometric profile of complicated circuits[6, 7]. For this purpose, magnetic powder is filled into thermoplastic polymer binder such as chlorinated polyethylene. In other words, this type of sheet is a kind of composite consisting of magnetic powder and thermoplastic polymer.

These days, this composite is further required to be more effective in noise suppression. In principle, the suppression depends on complex permeability of magnet that reveals the magnetizability in high frequency of electromagnetic wave[1, 8]. Hence, the filling proportion of magnetic powder should be so high as to raise up the ability for the suppression. However, the mixing process leads to void in the filler composites with high fraction of magnetic powder.

In this study, treatment of silane coupling agent to magnetic powder has been tried to depress the content of void yielding during the mixing process. Silane treatment is expected to give the surface of magnetic powder a high extent of affinity to binder polymer, chlorinated polyethylene (PE-Cl). In the treatment, a lot of kinds of silanes have been employed to make different affinity at the surface of the powder to the binder, as follows; alkyl ammonium cationic, amino, vinyl, methacryl, and epoxy silanes. To determine a degree of void in the composite sheet, densitometry has been used for calculation from the ratio of real density to theoretical one. In addition, the time dependence on viscosity of toluene solution including PE-Cl with silanes is determined

Fig. 1. Process flow for magnetic filler composite sheet.

to know the interaction between silane and the polymer. This determination has suggested that a sort of silanes lowers the viscosity during a mixing of silane-treated magnetic powder and polymer binder to prevent the growth of voids in the sheet.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

Magnetic powder used was a flat shape of Fe-Si-Al metal alloy powder. The density was 6.8 and the diameter was 31 μm in major axis. Binder polymer was PE-Cl with 1.1 of density. Silanes used was as follows; cationic type of octadecyldimethyl (3-(trimethoxysilyl) propyl) ammonium chloride (ODMAPS), basic type of aminopropyltriethoxysilane (APS), additionally reactive (vinyl) type of methacryoxylpropyltrimethoxysilane (MPS) and vinyl ethoxysilane (VS), and ring-opening type of glycidoxypyltrimethoxysilane (GPS). Other non-silane agents used was zinc stearate for practical surface treatment of popular inorganic fillers in performance of the filler-resin composites.

Total Procedure of Magnetic Powder Sheet

As shown in Fig. 1, the fabrication of magnetic powder-PE-Cl composite sheet was performed by the following three steps; surface treatment, mixing, and hot press.

Silane Treatment

Before surface treatment, a sort of silane chosen was stirred with water in a mole ratio 1:3 to be hydrolyzed at 30 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 1 hr for the activation to magnetic powder. One weight percent of silanes was added drop by drop to magnetic powder in a mixer for half an hour. After adding, the powder was dried in an oven at 100 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, and filtered through a sieve with 125 μm of sieve opening.

The fraction of silane chemically bonded to magnetic powder, called silane fixation, was determined as described in the previous paper [9].

Mixing and Hot Pressing

Silane-treated magnetic powder was mixed and kneaded into PE-Cl at 120 °C for 75 min using a kneader, Laboplasto-mil 30C 150, Toyo-Seiki Co. Ltd. to produce the magnetic powder-polymer composite compound. The mixing was carried out at the ratio of 93 wt% of magnetic powder to 7 wt% of PE-Cl (34:66 in volume fraction). This mixing combination was the highest content of non-treated magnetic powder to binder polymer. This fraction was kept even in other composites with silane-treated powder.

The obtained composite compounds were subjected to compression molding using a hot press (P36F3030, Shoji) at 190 °C of heating under 9.8 MPa of pressure to make a sheet with 0.5 mm in thickness.

Evaluation of Void in Sheet Composites

To evaluate void in the composite sheet, densinometry was carried out for the sheet. The fraction of void, V , was calculated from the experimental density, γ , as follows:

$$V=1 - \gamma/d \quad (1)$$

where d is the ideal density of composite sheet (93 wt% of fraction of magnetic powder) with free-void. The observation of void was practiced by a micro-focus X-ray image processor, SMX-1000, Shimadzu. Complex permeability was determined by a RF impedance materials analyzer (4291B, Hewlett-Packard).

Viscosity Measurement for PE-Cl Toluene Solution with Silanes

To clarify the reaction or the interaction of silanes in polymer binder, viscosity of toluene solution including 10 w/w% of PE-Cl was measured with addition of 0.25 w/w% of amino silanes such as APS, ODMAPS, and γ -(2-Aminoethyl)-aminopropyl-trimethoxysilane (DAPS). Liquid of silanes were used as received. In other case, silanes were hydrolyzed in the same manner as described in silane treatment. The measurement of viscosity was carried out at 50 r. p. m. using a B type of viscometer, B8R, Tokimeck Co. Ltd. equipped with a rotator for measurement range below 40000 mPa·s. This measurement was repeated for 3 days after mixing the solution.

Table 1. Dependence of silane treatment on density and void of magnetic filler composite sheet

Silane Coupling Agent	Experimental Density (g/cm ³)	Void* (%)
ODMAPS	3.96	18.2
APS	3.72	23.1
VS	3.66	24.4
MPS	3.67	24.2
GPS	3.65	24.5
Fatty Acid, Salt	3.30	31.8
untreated	3.63	25.0

* calculated from experimental and ideal densities.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Treatment Effect on Density of Composite

A lot of sheets of magnetic powder composites have been produced by the above procedure. The experimental density has been determined for each sheet to obtain the void fraction in the sheet. Table 1 shows silanes used in the treatment, the experimental density of sheet, and the void fraction calculated from the experimental and the ideal densities. The ideal density has been obtained from densities of magnetic powder and PE-Cl under no void. The ideal density in the blending ratio is 4.84, while the experimental densities for every silane treatment are less than this value. Silane-free sheet gives 3.63 of density. This means that there is 25.0 % of void in the sheet by the calculation. Compared with this value for silane-free sheet, fatty acid salt is rather counterproductive on disappearance of void. Some of silanes such as MPS, VS, and EPS are little effective in depression of void. Others, ODMAPS and APS are effective. In particular, ODMAPS is found to be useful for filling magnetic powder.

These results suggest that basicity is necessary for selecting the kind of silane. Taking the comparison between ODMAPS and fatty acid salt into consideration, long hydrocarbon chain such as octadecyl and stearyl groups may be a meaningless chemical structure in the effect on affinity to binder polymer PE-Cl. It may be preferable to have ionic group rather than basic group and alkyl group in the molecular structure of silanes. Thus, the ionic interaction is presumed to strongly occur between silanes and PE-Cl. Such a strong interaction leads to make magnetic powder surrounded by binder polymer.

Treatment Effect on Magnetic Permeability

In general, complex permeability of magnetic composites increases with content

Fig. 2. Frequency dependence of magnetic permeability for silane-treated filler composites.

Fig. 3. Void distribution in magnetic powder composite sheets observed from soft X-ray transmission images: ODMAPS used in silane treatment.

of magnetic materials. When magnetic materials is the same, resonance frequency of electromagnetic wave changes only the amplitude, and not the frequency range. In the same manner, the distribution of resonance frequency has a similar shape for every magnetic composite sheet, even though the amplitude, that is, complex permeability is changed. This means that maximum of permeability in frequency is treated as a representative value.

As shown in Fig. 2, the maximum value of magnetic permeability in real number increases with experimental density of composite sheet. It should be, then, noticed that silanes is possible to be distinguished to two class from a constant of proportionality: The former class includes ODMAPS and APS while the latter MPS, GPS, and untreated. The former class shows that the dependence of permeability on density is weaker than that in the latter class. This suggests that geometrical distribution of voids in a sheet is different between the classes. A larger void normally makes the permeability weaker, compared with small voids, even if total volumes of voids are the same. That is, this trend in proportionality supports that binder polymer is easily allocated around a magnetic particle in the former class such as ODMAPS and APS. Other silanes are useless for contact of binder polymer to the surface of a magnetic particle, which is rather aggregated in composite sheet.

Observation of Void Distribution

As mentioned above, basic or cationic silanes such as ODMAPS and APS seem to make the void distribution different from untreated composite sheet. To confirm the difference between them, soft X-ray transmittance images are obtained for both sheets. In untreated composite sheet, there are lots of white parts and black parts. White part indicates the location of a large void while black part arises from the aggregation of magnetic powder. That is, silane-free composite shows the occurrence of large voids and aggregation of powder in the sheet. On the other hand, silane-treated composite sheet shows low contrast in the image. This shows that such voids and aggregation are depressed by silane treatment. In addition, void distribution is not located. This phenomenon is supported to the proportionality between permeability and density, as described above.

Fig. 3. Time dependence on viscosity of polymer binder toluene solution added with ODMAPS (○, ●), APS (△, ▲), and DAPS(□, ■); open symbols gives hydrolyzed silane, and close ones silane liquid.

Silane Effect on Viscosity of Polymer Binder Solution

The organic groups of silanes affects the void growth in the sheet. In an assumption, if an organic group is strongly interacted with polymer binder, the silane bonded to magnetic filler attracts polymer binder near the surface of magnetic filler. This attraction can be considered to depress the void growth. From this viewpoint, the affinity of organic groups with polymer binder lowers the void fraction. Then, the resulting order in void fraction, as described above, gives the order of the affinity of silanes. In general, alkyl ammonium group of ODMAPS seems to be difficult to have stronger affinity than amino silane does.

In the above assumption, chemical bonded silane has an important role on the depression of void due to the attraction of polymer binder near the surface of magnetic filler. However, the fraction of silane chemically bonded to magnetic powder was 35.5 % in ODMAPS and 80.5 % in APS obtained in the manner as described in the previous paper [9]. In addition, the removal of physisorbed silane with organic solvent made the specific gravity changed 3.72 to 3.82 in APS, and 3.96 to 3.86 in ODMAPS. This means that ODMAPS seems to act contract to the assumption. Thus, in the case of ODMAPS, the physisorbed silane seems to have an important role on the depression of void.

To know the effect of physisorbed silane on void growth, the viscosity of polymer binder toluene solution has been measured with silanes such as ODMAPS, APS, and DAPS. In the addition of silane to the solution, two states of silane has been used: One is liquid as received, and the other is hydrolyzed for the activation to the bonding to magnetic powder due to silanol group of silane. Each silane changes the viscosity of the polymer binder solution, as shown in Fig. 4. In APS and ADPS, liquid

and hydrolyzed types of silanes raise the viscosity. In fact, the presence of both silanes have the solution including PE-Cl gelled except DAPS liquid. It should be noted that hydrolyzed silanes advance the gelation, compared with liquid ones.

These results mean that silane has a role as a cross-linking agent. In this case, inorganic groups of silanes, such as alkoxysilane and silanol, should be chemically condensed to form linkage with siloxane bonding [10]. Hence, hydrolyzed silane has some silanol groups from the beginning in stirring so as to make linkage easily. On the other hand, organic groups of silanes are generally of chemical bond or of physicochemical bond to polymer binder, such as ionic interaction and hydrogen bonding. Thus, the bonding strength of the interaction between organic groups of silanes makes cross-linking easily together with siloxane bond between silane. Eventually, APS and ADPS are so strong as to make the interaction with polymer binder, resulting in the gelation of the polymer solution. Taking this into consideration, silane is difficult to depress voids in magnetic filler – polymer binder sheet.

However, ODMAPS has the viscosity lowered for long stock time, even though the silane increases the viscosity by little for the initial time. This can be interpreted in terms of the linkage with siloxane between silane molecules and the strength of the interaction. ODMAPS has a normal alkoxysilane group, while the large organic group of ODMAPS is not so strong to make the interaction with polymer binder. Eventually, ODMAPS shows that the viscosity increases slowly due to the weak interaction. At the same time, the linkage between silanes makes the organic group of silane apart from polymer binder, and finally a large size of silane condensates is produced without the interaction with polymer binder, and decreases the viscosity. Such silane condensates may have a role like molecular rolling friction [11].

The behavior on the viscosity of the polymer binding solution with silanes reflects the void growth in the magnetic filler sheet, as described above. Taking it into consideration that APS and DAPS hydrolyzed raise the viscosity, physisorbed silane near the surface of magnetic filler gives too high viscosity to bury voids, even though chemical-bonded one attracts polymer binder at the surface. On the other hand, ODMAPS has local viscosity lower after long time in mixing process so that voids are easily disappeared with such a fluid polymer.

Though the above mechanism has never been discussed, silane, in particular, physisorbed one has been found to have an important role to depress the fraction of voids in the filler polymeric composites.

CONCLUSION

As summarized in surface treatment of magnetic powder with a lot of kinds of silanes, the fraction of voids in the composite sheet and the magnetic permeability of the sheet lead to the following conclusion:

1. Silane treatment makes the density higher and the void fraction lower for the sheet produced by hot press molding
2. Ionic and basic type of silanes such as ODMAPS and APS are effective in the disappearance of void in the sheet. This effect is suggested to depend on the ionic

interaction between organic group of silane and end groups of binder polymer.

3. Magnetic permeability of the composite sheet is proportional to the experimental density that increased with silanes. However, silanes are distinguished to two classes from the proportionality. This trend suggests strong interaction due to ionic and basic silanes. Thus, such silanes depress the occurrence of voids in the sheet.
4. The effect of silanes on void has been by soft X-ray transmission image processor. As a result, ionic silane, ODMAPS, makes voids small and distributed homogeneously in the sheet. Therefore, ionic property due to organic group of silanes has a useful role on the improvement of magnetic permeability in the production of magnetic sheet kneaded with a similar type of binder polymer.
5. The effect of physisorbed silane on the void disappearance has been discussed from the time dependence on viscosity of polymer binder solution added with silane. As a result, silane having weak bond strength to polymer is possible to lowers the viscosity near the powder, decreasing the void fraction. This mechanism may be applied to the process for filler composites.

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